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Comparative Seismic Study of RC High-Rise (UG + G + 7) Structures with Varying Plan, Beam, and Column Section Configurations under Earthquake Loading

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a comparative seismic analysis of reinforced concrete (RC) high-rise framed structures subjected to earthquake loading under different seismic zones. The primary objective of the work is to evaluate the influence of plan dimensions and structural configuration on the seismic response of multi-storey RC buildings. For the present investigation, six analytical models were considered and classified into Part A and Part B configurations. The Part A models were developed with plan dimensions of 34 m × 38 m, while the Part B models were modeled with dimensions of 44 m × 38 m. All the building models were maintained with a uniform height of 37.3 m and configured as UG + G + 7 storeys in order to maintain consistency during comparative analysis.

The analytical modelling and seismic analysis were carried out using ETABS software in accordance with the provisions of IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 [17]. The structures were modeled as RC framed buildings using M40 grade concrete and HYSD Fe-500 reinforcement. The analysis was performed for Seismic Zone II, Zone III, and Zone IV considering Type II medium soil conditions [17]. Various structural response parameters such as storey displacement, storey drift, base shear, and base reaction were evaluated to study the seismic behaviour of the models.

The results obtained from the analysis indicate that the displacement and storey drift values increase progressively with the increase in seismic intensity from Zone II to Zone IV. The maximum storey displacement observed in the study was 272.198 mm for the Part A model under Zone IV conditions, whereas the corresponding displacement for the

Part B model was found to be 175.514 mm. Similarly, the maximum storey drift recorded for the Part A model was 0.010253, while the Part B model showed a comparatively lower drift value of 0.006638 under the same loading condition. The base shear values also increased

significantly with seismic zone intensity. For the Part A model, the base shear increased from 4405.96 kN in Zone II to 9913.42 kN in Zone IV, whereas the Part B model exhibited higher base shear values ranging from 10874 kN to 24466 kN due to larger seismic weight and plan dimensions.

Keywords: Reinforced concrete structure, seismic analysis, storey drift, base shear, ETABS, high-rise building, seismic zones, structural response

INTRODUCTION

Earthquakes are among the most destructive natural hazards affecting human life, infrastructure, and the economy. Rapid urbanization and population growth have resulted in a significant increase in the construction of multi-storey and high-rise reinforced concrete (RC) buildings, particularly in urban regions. Many of these structures are located in earthquake-prone areas where seismic forces become a critical factor in structural design [3], [4]. During an earthquake, buildings are subjected to dynamic lateral forces generated due to ground motion, which may cause excessive displacement, storey drift, structural damage, or even collapse if the structure is not properly designed [5], [15]. Therefore, understanding the seismic behaviour of high-rise buildings has become one of the most important aspects of structural engineering.

The response of a building during an earthquake mainly depends on factors such as structural configuration, building height, stiffness, mass distribution, plan dimensions, material properties, and the type of lateral load-resisting system used in the structure [7], [8], [14]. In high-rise buildings, lateral loads produced by earthquakes often govern the structural design more critically than gravity loads. As the height of the building increases, the flexibility of the structure also increases,

leading to larger lateral displacements and inter-storey drifts [15], [16]. Hence, proper structural planning and seismic-resistant design are essential to improve the safety and performance of buildings under earthquake loading conditions.

Reinforced concrete framed structures are widely used in modern construction due to their durability, strength, economy, and ease of construction. In RC framed buildings, beams and columns are connected rigidly to transfer gravity and lateral loads safely to the foundation. Depending upon the seismic detailing and ductility requirements, moment-resisting frames are generally classified into Ordinary Moment Resisting Frames (OMRF) and Special Moment Resisting Frames (SMRF). OMRF structures are designed according to conventional design provisions and possess limited ductility, whereas SMRF structures are specially detailed as per seismic design codes to achieve higher ductility and improved energy dissipation capacity during earthquakes [18].

Among different structural systems, shear walls, bracing systems, and moment-resisting frames are commonly adopted to resist lateral seismic forces in high-rise buildings [5], [7], [14]. Shear walls provide high stiffness and effectively reduce lateral displacement and storey drift. Bracing systems improve structural

stability and enhance energy dissipation under seismic excitation. Moment-resisting frames, on the other hand, provide flexibility and ductile behaviour through rigid beam-column connections. The performance of these systems varies depending on building geometry, loading conditions, and seismic intensity. Therefore, comparative analysis of different structural configurations becomes necessary to identify efficient and economical structural systems for seismic-resistant design.

In recent years, advanced structural analysis software has enabled engineers to perform detailed analytical studies of complex structures subjected to dynamic loading. ETABS software is widely used for modelling and seismic analysis of high-rise buildings due to its efficiency in evaluating structural response parameters such as displacement, storey drift, base shear, storey shear, and base reaction [4], [5], [13]. The software allows accurate modelling of RC framed structures under different seismic loading conditions in accordance with codal provisions.

The present study focuses on the comparative seismic analysis of six RC high-rise building models categorized into Part A and Part B configurations. The models under Part A were developed with plan dimensions of 34 m × 38 m, whereas the models under Part B were modeled with dimensions of 44 m × 38 m. All the analytical models were maintained at a constant height of 37.3 m with UG + G + 7 storey configuration. The seismic analysis was carried out for Seismic Zone II, Zone III, and Zone IV as per the provisions of IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 [17] considering Type II medium soil conditions.

Seismic Behaviour of High-Rise Buildings

High-rise buildings are highly sensitive to seismic forces because of their greater

height, flexibility, and large mass concentration [3], [4]. During an earthquake, ground motion induces lateral forces in the structure, resulting in displacement, storey drift, base shear, and overturning moments. Unlike low-rise buildings, high-rise structures possess longer natural time periods and experience significant dynamic effects under seismic excitation [15], [16]. Therefore, proper seismic analysis and structural design are essential to ensure stability, safety, and serviceability during earthquake loading conditions. The general seismic behaviour and response mechanism of high-rise buildings under earthquake loading are illustrated in Figure 1.

According to IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 [17], seismic forces acting on buildings depend on important parameters such as seismic zone factor, importance factor, response reduction factor, soil condition, and structural configuration. Buildings located in higher seismic zones are subjected to larger lateral forces and require enhanced stiffness and ductility to resist earthquake effects effectively. The code specifies permissible limits for displacement and storey drift to prevent structural and non-structural damage during seismic events.

One of the major seismic response parameters in high-rise buildings is lateral displacement. Excessive displacement may reduce structural stability and cause discomfort to occupants. Similarly, inter-storey drift plays a crucial role in seismic performance, as large drift values may lead to cracking in beams, columns, masonry walls, and failure of beam-column joints [5], [7], [8]. Therefore, controlling displacement and drift is an important aspect of earthquake-resistant design.

The seismic behaviour of high-rise buildings is significantly influenced by the type of lateral load-resisting system adopted in the structure. Systems such as shear walls, bracing systems, and moment-

resisting frames improve the lateral stiffness and energy dissipation capacity of buildings [5], [14]. Special Moment Resisting Frames (SMRF), detailed according to IS 13920: 2016 [18], provide improved ductility and better seismic resistance under severe earthquake conditions.

Modern structural analysis software such as ETABS enables accurate modelling and seismic evaluation of high-rise structures. The analysis helps engineers assess parameters such as displacement, storey drift, base shear, and structural stability, leading to safer and more economical earthquake-resistant designs [4], [5], [13].

Fig. 1: Seismic Behaviour of High-Rise Buildings under Earthquake Loading.

ETABS Software

ETABS (Extended Three-Dimensional Analysis of Building Systems) is one of the most widely used structural engineering software applications for the analysis and design of multi-storey and high-rise buildings. The software is developed by Computers and Structures, Inc. and is specially designed for modelling complex building structures subjected to gravity, wind, and seismic loads [17].

One of the major advantages of ETABS is its capability to perform advanced seismic analysis according to international and Indian Standard codes. The software supports linear static analysis, response spectrum analysis, nonlinear analysis, and time history analysis for evaluating the seismic behaviour of structures. In accordance with IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 [17], ETABS can evaluate important seismic response parameters such as base

shear, storey displacement, storey drift, modal time period, and storey shear. The software also supports ductile detailing considerations as specified in IS 13920: 2016 [18].

In the present study, ETABS software has been used for modelling and seismic analysis of six RC building models categorized under Part A and Part B configurations. The analysis was carried out for Seismic Zone II, Zone III, and Zone IV considering Type II medium soil conditions [17]. The software was utilized to evaluate important response parameters such as displacement, maximum storey drift, base shear, seismic weight, and base reaction under earthquake loading conditions.

Due to its analytical accuracy, user-friendly interface, and efficient modelling capabilities, ETABS has become an essential software tool for structural

engineers involved in the analysis, design, and seismic assessment of high-rise buildings [4], [5], [13].

Selection of Different Beam and Column Sizes

In high-rise reinforced concrete (RC) buildings, the use of identical beam and column sizes throughout the structure is generally uneconomical and may lead to unnecessary increase in construction cost. The magnitude of structural loading varies at different storey levels depending on gravity loads, seismic forces, span length, and load distribution. Therefore, providing the same beam and column dimensions for all structural members results in excessive material consumption and inefficient structural design.

Beam dimensions were also varied based on span length and loading conditions. Larger beam sections were adopted in heavily loaded regions and longer spans to improve flexural strength, stiffness, and load-carrying capacity. The variation in beam and column sizes helps in reducing excessive material usage while maintaining adequate structural safety and seismic resistance.

The beam sizes considered in the present analytical models are: 230 × 530 mm, 230 × 600 mm, 300 × 600 mm, 300 × 650 mm, 300 × 700 mm, 300 × 750 mm, 300 × 900 mm, 300 × 1200 mm, 350 × 600 mm, 400 × 600 mm, 400 × 750 mm, 400 × 900 mm, and 450 × 600 mm.

Similarly, the column sizes adopted in the study include: 350 × 600 mm, 450 × 750 mm, 450 × 800 mm, 450 × 900 mm, 450 × 1000 mm, 450 × 1200 mm, 550 × 550 mm, 600 × 600 mm, 650 × 650 mm, 700 × 700 mm, 750 × 750 mm, 850 × 850 mm, and 1000 × 1000 mm.

The selected beam and column dimensions were assigned in ETABS during modelling

and seismic analysis to achieve realistic structural behaviour under earthquake loading conditions. Proper selection of sectional dimensions improves stiffness, controls displacement and storey drift, and enhances the overall seismic performance of high-rise RC framed structures [3], [5], [7].

Problem Statement

In recent years, rapid urbanization and population growth have led to the increasing construction of high-rise reinforced concrete (RC) buildings in urban and seismic-prone regions. These structures are highly vulnerable to earthquake-induced lateral forces because of their greater height, flexibility, and mass concentration [3], [4]. During seismic events, high-rise buildings experience significant displacement, storey drift, base shear, and overturning effects, which may result in structural damage or instability if the building is not properly designed [5], [15].

The seismic response of a building is greatly influenced by factors such as plan dimensions, structural configuration, stiffness, mass distribution, and the type of lateral load-resisting system adopted in the structure [7], [8], [14]. Variations in these parameters can considerably affect the overall structural performance under earthquake loading. Buildings with inadequate stiffness or improper configuration are more susceptible to excessive lateral displacement and drift, leading to cracking in structural members, damage to non-structural components, and possible structural failure [3], [16].

Although various studies have been carried out on seismic analysis of RC framed structures, limited comparative research is available on the influence of different plan dimensions and structural configurations while maintaining the same building height and loading conditions [4], [5]. In

many practical situations, engineers face difficulties in selecting suitable structural configurations that provide adequate seismic resistance along with economy and structural efficiency.

Therefore, there is a need to evaluate and compare the seismic behaviour of high-rise RC framed buildings with different plan dimensions under varying seismic zones. The present study focuses on the comparative seismic analysis of six RC building models categorized into Part A and Part B configurations using ETABS. The models are analyzed under Seismic Zone II, Zone III, and Zone IV conditions as per IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 [17] to study important response parameters such as displacement, storey drift, base shear, seismic weight, and base reaction.

Scope of Study

The present study focuses on the seismic analysis and comparative evaluation of reinforced concrete (RC) high-rise framed buildings subjected to earthquake loading conditions. The scope of the work includes analytical modelling, seismic response assessment, and comparison of structural behaviour for different building configurations under various seismic zones [17].

In this study, a total of six RC building models are considered and categorized into Part A and Part B configurations. The models under Part A are developed with plan dimensions of 34 m × 38 m, whereas the Part B models are modeled with dimensions of 44 m × 38 m. All the analytical models are maintained with a constant building height of 37.3 m and configured as UG + G + 7 storeys to ensure uniformity in vertical geometry during comparative analysis.

The structural analysis is carried out using ETABS software in accordance with the provisions of IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 and

relevant Indian Standard codes [17]. The seismic performance of the structures is evaluated for Seismic Zone II, Zone III, and Zone IV considering Type II medium soil conditions [17].

The scope of the study mainly includes:

1. Modelling and analysis of RC framed high-rise buildings using ETABS software.
2. Comparative evaluation of Part A and Part B building configurations.
3. Assessment of seismic response parameters such as displacement, storey drift, base shear, seismic weight, and base reaction.
4. Study of the influence of plan dimensions and structural stiffness on seismic performance.
5. Evaluation of structural behaviour under different seismic zones.
6. Identification of comparatively efficient structural configuration for earthquake-resistant design.

The present investigation is limited to linear static seismic analysis of RC framed structures. Factors such as soil-structure interaction, nonlinear material behaviour, wind analysis, foundation design, and construction sequence effects are not considered in the present study. The findings obtained from this research may be useful for structural engineers and researchers involved in the planning, analysis, and seismic design of high-rise RC buildings in earthquake-prone regions.

Importance of Study

Earthquakes are one of the most destructive natural hazards affecting the safety and stability of structures, particularly high-rise buildings located in seismic-prone regions. With the rapid growth of urbanization and increasing demand for vertical construction, the seismic performance of reinforced concrete (RC) buildings has become an important area of research in structural

engineering [4], [15]. High-rise buildings are more susceptible to lateral forces generated during earthquakes due to their increased height, flexibility, and mass concentration [3], [16]. Therefore, understanding the behaviour of such structures under seismic loading is essential for ensuring structural safety and minimizing structural damage.

The importance of the present study lies in evaluating the seismic response of RC framed high-rise buildings with different plan dimensions and structural configurations. Comparative seismic analysis helps in understanding how variations in stiffness, geometry, and mass distribution influence important response parameters such as displacement, storey drift, base shear, and base reaction [5], [7], [8]. The study provides valuable information regarding the structural behaviour of buildings subjected to different seismic zone conditions.

The investigation also highlights the significance of proper seismic-resistant design as per IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 [17] and ductile detailing provisions of IS 13920: 2016 [18]. By analyzing the response of buildings in Seismic Zone II, Zone III, and Zone IV, the study helps in understanding the effect of increasing seismic intensity on the structural performance of high-rise RC buildings.

Another important aspect of the study is the use of advanced structural analysis software such as ETABS for modelling and evaluating complex structural behaviour under earthquake loading. The study demonstrates how analytical tools can be effectively used to predict seismic response and improve structural design efficiency [4], [5], [13].

The findings of the present research may assist structural engineers, researchers, and designers in selecting suitable structural

configurations for earthquake-resistant construction. The study may also contribute to safer, economical, and efficient design practices for high-rise buildings located in seismic regions [14], [16].

LITERATURE REVIEW

A comprehensive literature survey was carried out to understand the seismic behaviour of reinforced concrete (RC) high-rise buildings subjected to earthquake loading conditions. More than 30 national and international research papers related to seismic analysis, shear walls, bracing systems, moment-resisting frames, structural irregularities, and lateral load-resisting systems were critically reviewed to identify the research gap and define the objectives of the present study. In addition, a separate review paper based on seismic performance of high-rise RC buildings and structural systems was also prepared and published as part of the present research work.

The reviewed studies indicate that the seismic response of high-rise buildings is mainly influenced by structural configuration, stiffness, mass distribution, building height, plan dimensions, and the type of lateral load-resisting system adopted in the structure. Researchers have widely used advanced analytical software such as ETABS, SAP2000, STAAD. Pro, ANSYS, and Robot Structural Analysis for modelling and evaluating the seismic behaviour of structures under different loading conditions.

N. Perkovic et al. [1] investigated the fire resistance and structural behaviour of load-bearing composite timber-glass wall systems under thermal and mechanical loading. The study highlighted the importance of load redistribution and protective detailing for improving structural stability under extreme conditions. P. Teymur [2] studied the

influence of soil improvement and retrofitting techniques on reinforced concrete buildings subjected to seismic loading and reported that soil stabilization significantly reduces inter-storey drift and foundation instability.

M. Aslani and P. Tehrani [3] evaluated the seismic response and collapse capacity of RC buildings with vertical irregularities in shear walls using nonlinear dynamic analysis. The results indicated that lower-storey irregularities considerably increase seismic demand and structural vulnerability. K. K. Sharma et al. [4] carried out displacement-based seismic fragility assessment of high-rise RC buildings and concluded that irregular buildings are more susceptible to seismic damage under severe earthquake conditions.

Araj T. A. Sayyed and S. B. Tanawade [5] investigated the seismic performance of buildings with bracing systems and shear walls under different soil conditions. The study reported that hybrid structural systems improve stiffness and reduce lateral displacement more effectively than conventional framed systems. X. Zhao and J. M. Ding [6] focused on wind-resistant structural design of super-tall buildings and emphasized the importance of lateral stiffness and structural stability in tall structures.

Y. Cheng [7] analyzed the seismic behaviour of shear wall systems in high-rise buildings and observed significant reduction in displacement and storey drift due to increased stiffness. Y. Uysal [8] studied the effect of shear wall ratio on seismic performance and concluded that increasing the wall ratio considerably improves structural stiffness and lateral resistance.

A. Wenzel et al. [9] investigated the structural optimization of timber buildings

and highlighted the importance of efficient structural systems for improving building performance and sustainability. A. S. Mansour et al. [10] evaluated progressive collapse behaviour in steel structures subjected to blast loading and emphasized the role of structural continuity and redundancy in preventing collapse.

K. Fujii [11] studied the seismic capacity of reinforced concrete moment-resisting frames with steel damper columns and observed improved energy dissipation and seismic resistance. D. M. de Lima et al. [12] analyzed composite steel and concrete multi-storey buildings and concluded that composite systems provide better structural efficiency and load-carrying capacity.

J. Liu [13] investigated the application of outrigger and belt truss systems in high-rise buildings and reported considerable reduction in lateral displacement and overturning effects. K. H. Kim [14] studied hybrid shear wall and bracing systems and observed enhanced stiffness and improved seismic behaviour due to effective lateral force distribution.

S. Patel and R. Mehta [15] evaluated the effect of wind and seismic loads on multi-storey buildings and concluded that lateral load effects become increasingly critical with increase in building height. A. Dushimimana et al. [16] investigated the influence of seismic loads on base isolation systems and reported significant reduction in structural acceleration and seismic response.

The seismic analysis and earthquake-resistant design provisions specified in IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 [17] provide guidelines for evaluating seismic forces and structural response of buildings. Ductile detailing requirements specified in IS 13920: 2016 [18] improve energy dissipation capacity and prevent brittle

failure during earthquake excitation. The design of reinforced concrete members is carried out according to IS 456: 2000 [19], while structural loading conditions are considered based on IS 875 [20].

From the reviewed literature, it is observed that structural configuration, stiffness, seismic zone intensity, and lateral load-resisting systems significantly influence the seismic behaviour of high-rise buildings. However, limited studies are available on the comparative seismic assessment of RC high-rise buildings with different plan dimensions while maintaining identical building height and loading conditions. Therefore, the present study focuses on the comparative seismic analysis of Part A and Part B RC building models under Seismic Zone II, Zone III, and Zone IV conditions using ETABS software. The investigation mainly evaluates displacement, storey drift, base shear, seismic weight, and base reaction to study the influence of plan dimensions and structural stiffness on seismic performance.

Research Gap

From the detailed review of previous studies, it is observed that considerable research has been carried out on the seismic analysis of reinforced concrete high-rise buildings using different structural systems such as shear walls, bracing systems, moment-resisting frames, and hybrid structural configurations [5], [7], [8], [14]. Many researchers have evaluated seismic response parameters including displacement, storey drift, base shear, stiffness, and natural time period under earthquake loading conditions [3], [4], [15], [16].

Several investigations focused on the effect of structural irregularities, soil conditions, damping systems, and retrofitting techniques on the seismic performance of buildings [2], [3], [11].

Advanced structural analysis software such as ETABS, SAP2000, and STAAD.Pro were widely used for analytical modelling and seismic assessment of structures. Most of the available studies mainly concentrated on either a single structural configuration or specific lateral load-resisting systems [5], [7], [13].

However, limited research is available on the comparative seismic evaluation of RC high-rise framed buildings with different plan dimensions while maintaining identical building height, loading conditions, and material properties [4], [15]. Very few studies have investigated the influence of plan dimensions and structural stiffness on seismic behaviour under multiple seismic zones using a uniform structural configuration with different beam & column sizes in one plan.

In addition, comparatively less attention has been given to the assessment of seismic response parameters such as displacement, maximum storey drift, base shear, seismic weight, and base reaction for buildings having different plan configurations under Seismic Zone II, Zone III, and Zone IV conditions [3], [5], [16]. Most of the existing studies also focus on irregular structures, whereas limited work has been reported on comparative evaluation of regular RC framed high-rise buildings with varying plan dimensions.

Therefore, the present study aims to bridge this research gap by carrying out a comparative seismic analysis of six RC high-rise building models categorized as Part A and Part B using ETABS software. The investigation focuses on evaluating the effect of plan dimensions and structural stiffness on the seismic performance of buildings subjected to different seismic zone conditions in accordance with IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 [17] and ductile

detailing provisions of IS 13920: 2016 [18].

Objectives of Study

1. To analyze the seismic behaviour of reinforced concrete (RC) high-rise framed buildings under Seismic Zone II, Zone III, and Zone IV conditions in accordance with IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 [17].
2. To develop and evaluate Part A and Part B RC building models with different plan dimensions using ETABS software.
3. To assess important seismic response parameters such as displacement, storey drift, base shear, seismic weight, and base reaction for all analytical models [3], [4], [5].
4. To compare the seismic performance of buildings with different structural stiffness and plan configurations under identical loading conditions [7], [8], [14].
5. To study the influence of increasing seismic intensity on the overall behaviour and stability of RC high-rise buildings [15], [16].
6. To identify the comparatively efficient structural configuration for earthquake-resistant design based on seismic response and structural performance.

SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT

General

The present study focuses on the development and seismic analysis of

reinforced concrete (RC) high-rise building models using ETABS. A total of six analytical models were developed and categorized into Part A and Part B configurations. The modelling and analysis were carried out to evaluate the seismic behaviour of high-rise RC framed structures subjected to earthquake loading under different seismic zones [17].

The analytical models were developed considering identical structural height, loading conditions, material properties, and seismic parameters to achieve a reliable comparative evaluation. The structures were analyzed under Seismic Zone II, Zone III, and Zone IV conditions in accordance with IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 [17].

Description of Building Models

For the present investigation, six RC high-rise building models were considered for seismic analysis. The models were classified into two groups, namely Part A and Part B Figure 2 & 3.

- **Part A Models:** Plan dimensions of 34 m × 38 m
- **Part B Models:** Plan dimensions of 44 m × 38 m

All the analytical models were maintained with a uniform building height of 37.3 m and configured as UG + G + 7 storeys. The buildings were modeled as RC framed structures consisting of beams, columns, and slabs.

Fig. 2: Plan view for Part A.

Fig. 3: Plan view for Part B.

Fig. 4: 3-D Plan view for Part A.

Fig. 5: 3-D Plan view for Part B.

Structural Modelling

The structural modelling was carried out using ETABS software by defining material properties, sectional dimensions, loading conditions, and seismic parameters. The buildings were modeled using three-dimensional space frame elements to simulate realistic structural behaviour under earthquake loading.

The structural members were assigned according to loading requirements and span conditions. Various beam and column sizes were considered during modelling to ensure structural stability and accurate load transfer.

Material properties

- Grade of Concrete: M40 [19]
- Reinforcement Steel: HYSD Fe-500
- Density of Concrete: 25 kN/m³ [19]
- Density of Brick Masonry: 20 kN/m³ [19]

Structural details

- Slab Thickness: 150 mm [19]
- Wall Thickness: 230 mm [19]
- Storey Height: 4.2 m
- Total Height: 37.3 m

Loading Considerations

The structural models were analyzed by considering gravity loads and seismic loads as per Indian Standard code provisions[17].

Dead Load

Dead load includes self-weight of structural components such as beams, columns, slabs, and walls. The self-weight of the structure was automatically calculated by ETABS software based on material density and sectional dimensions.

Live Load

A live load of 5.0 kN/m² was considered for all floor levels according to IS 875 [20].

Seismic Load

Seismic loading was applied according to IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 [17] considering:

- Seismic Zone II
- Seismic Zone III
- Seismic Zone IV
- Importance Factor = 1.0
- Response Reduction Factor = 5.0
- Soil Type = Type II Medium Soil

Table 1: Specification RC Frame Structure.

Particulars	Details
Type of Structure	RCC UG + G + 7 Building
Configuration	UG + G + 7
Type of Frame	Framed Structure
Total Height of Building	37.3 m
Height of Each Storey	4.2 m
Plan Dimensions of Building	Part A: 34 m × 38 m ; Part B: 44 m × 38 m
Thickness of Walls	230 mm [19].
Beam Sizes	230×530 mm, 230×600 mm, 300×600 mm, 300×650 mm, 300×700 mm, 300×750 mm, 300×900 mm, 300×1200 mm, 350×600 mm, 400×600 mm, 400×750 mm, 400×900 mm, 450×600 mm
Column Sizes	350×600 mm, 450×750 mm, 450×800 mm, 450×900 mm, 450×1000 mm, 450×1200 mm, 550×550 mm, 600×600 mm, 650×650 mm, 700×700 mm, 750×750 mm, 850×850 mm, 1000×1000 mm
Slab Thickness	150 mm thick RCC slab [19]
Live Load	5.0 kN/m ²
Grade of Concrete	M-40 [19]
Grade of Reinforcement	HYSD Fe-500
Density of Concrete	25 kN/m ³ [19]
Density of Brick Masonry	20 kN/m ³ [19]
Seismic Zones Considered	Zone II, Zone III, and Zone IV [17]
Soil Type	Type II – Medium Soil [17]
Importance Factor (I)	1.0 [17]
Response Reduction Factor (R)	5.0 [17]
Seismic Zone Factor	0.10 for Zone II, 0.16 for Zone III, and 0.24 for Zone IV [17]

Analysis Procedure

The seismic analysis of the building models was performed using linear static analysis methods in ETABS software. The analytical procedure involved:

1. Development of three-dimensional structural models.
2. Assignment of material properties and sectional dimensions [19].
3. Application of gravity and seismic loads [17], [19].
4. Definition of seismic parameters according to IS code provisions [17].
5. Execution of analysis for different seismic zones [17].

6. Evaluation of structural response parameters.

Comparative Evaluation

The analytical results obtained from Part A and Part B models were compared to study the influence of plan dimensions and structural stiffness on seismic behaviour. Comparative evaluation was carried out for different seismic zones [17], to identify the structural configuration exhibiting better seismic performance and stability under earthquake loading conditions [17].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

General

The present chapter discusses the analytical results obtained from the seismic analysis of reinforced concrete (RC) high-rise building models developed using ETABS. A total of six analytical models categorized under Part A and Part B configurations were analyzed under Seismic Zone II, Zone III, and Zone IV conditions in accordance with IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 [17].

Displacement Results in X-Direction (EQX)

Storey displacement is one of the most important seismic response parameters used to evaluate the lateral movement of structures subjected to earthquake loading. Excessive displacement may lead to structural instability, discomfort to occupants, and damage to non-structural components. The displacement values obtained from the analysis for Part A and

Part B models under different seismic zones are presented in **Table 2**, while the comparative graphical representation of displacement variation is illustrated in **Figure 6**.

The results indicate that storey displacement increases progressively from lower storeys to upper storeys for all analytical models. It is also observed that displacement values increase significantly with increase in seismic zone intensity from Zone II to Zone IV.

The maximum displacement observed in the study is 272.198 mm for the Part A model under Seismic Zone IV conditions, whereas the corresponding displacement for the Part B model was found to be 175.514 mm. The Part B models exhibited comparatively lower displacement values due to improved structural stiffness and larger plan dimensions.

Table 2: Displacement Results in X-Direction (EQX).

Storey Level	1 PART A (mm)	1 PART B (mm)	2 PART A (mm)	2 PART B (mm)	3 PART A (mm)	3 PART B (mm)
LMR	116.476	79.971	174.715	119.956	262.072	179.934
Terrace Floor	120.977	78.006	181.465	117.009	272.198	175.514
6th Floor	109.831	72.600	164.747	108.900	247.120	163.350
5th Floor	95.895	64.921	143.843	97.382	215.765	146.073
4th Floor	79.123	55.060	118.685	82.590	178.027	123.885
3rd Floor	60.492	43.637	90.738	65.455	136.107	98.183
2nd Floor	41.354	31.245	62.031	46.868	93.046	70.302
1st Floor	23.229	19.002	34.843	28.503	52.264	42.755
Ground Floor	8.231	7.406	12.346	11.110	18.520	16.664
Base	0	0	0	0	0	0

Fig. 6: Displacement Results in X-Direction (EQX).

Max Storey Drift Results in X-Direction (EQX)

Storey drift represents the relative displacement between consecutive floors during earthquake excitation. It is an important parameter governing the seismic safety and serviceability of buildings. Excessive drift may lead to cracking of structural members, damage to masonry walls, and failure of beam-column joints. The maximum storey drift values obtained from the analysis are presented in **Table 3**, whereas the comparative drift behaviour is illustrated in **Figure 7**.

The analytical results indicate that storey drift values increase gradually from the base level towards the middle and upper storeys. Similar to displacement behaviour, drift values also increased with increase in seismic intensity.

The maximum storey drift recorded in this study 0.010253 for the Part A model under Zone IV conditions, whereas the Part B model exhibited a comparatively lower drift value of 0.006638. This indicates that Part B models provide better lateral stiffness and improved resistance against earthquake-induced deformation.

Table 3: Maximum Storey Drift Results in X-Direction (EQX).

Storey Level	1 PART A	1 PART B	2 PART A	2 PART B	3 PART A	3 PART B
LMR	0.002447	0.000931	0.003671	0.001396	0.005507	0.002094
Terrace Floor	0.002654	0.001296	0.003981	0.001944	0.005971	0.002916
6th Floor	0.003318	0.001828	0.004977	0.002742	0.007466	0.004114
5th Floor	0.003993	0.002348	0.005990	0.003522	0.008985	0.005283
4th Floor	0.004436	0.002720	0.006654	0.004080	0.009981	0.006119
3rd Floor	0.004557	0.002950	0.006835	0.004426	0.010253	0.006638
2nd Floor	0.004316	0.002951	0.006473	0.004427	0.009710	0.006640
1st Floor	0.003571	0.002845	0.005356	0.004267	0.008034	0.006401
Ground Floor	0.001789	0.001610	0.002684	0.002415	0.004026	0.003623
Base	0	0	0	0	0	0

Fig. 7: Maximum Storey Drift Results in X-Direction (EQX).

Base Shear Results in X-Direction (EQX)

Base shear represents the total lateral seismic force acting at the base of the structure during earthquake loading. It is one of the major parameters considered in seismic design according to IS code provisions. The comparative base shear values obtained from the analysis are presented in **Table 4**, while the graphical comparison of base shear variation for different seismic zones is illustrated in **Figure 8**.

The analysis results indicate that base shear values increase significantly with increase in seismic zone intensity. For the Part A model, the base shear increased from 4405.96 kN in Seismic Zone II to 9913.42 kN in Seismic Zone IV. Similarly, the Part B model exhibited higher base shear values ranging from 10874 kN to 24466 kN due to larger seismic weight and plan dimensions.

The higher base shear observed in Part B models indicates greater seismic force demand because of increased building mass and structural dimensions.

Table 4: Base Shear Results.

Seismic Zone	Part A Model – Base Shear (kN)	Part B Model – Base Shear (kN)
Seismic Zone II	4405.96	10874
Seismic Zone III	6608.00	16311
Seismic Zone IV	9913.42	24466

Fig. 8: Base Shear Results.

Base Reaction

Base reaction represents the total support reaction developed at the foundation level due to structural loading and seismic effects. The comparative base reaction values obtained from the analysis are presented in **Table 5**, while the variation in base reaction for Part A and Part B models is illustrated in **Figure 9**.

The analytical results indicate that the Part B models developed higher base reaction values compared to Part A models because of larger structural dimensions and seismic weight.

The maximum base reaction observed for the Part A model was 173617.56 kN, whereas the Part B model exhibited a base reaction value of 313286.08 kN.

Table 5: Base Reaction.

Seismic Zone	Part A Model – Base Reaction (kN)	Part B Model – Base Reaction (kN)
Seismic Zone II	173617.56 kN	313286.08 kN
Seismic Zone III	173617.56 kN	313286.08 kN
Seismic Zone IV	173617.56 kN	313286.08 kN

Fig. 9: Base Reaction.

Comparative Discussion

The comparative seismic analysis of Part A and Part B RC high-rise building models indicates that plan dimensions and structural stiffness significantly influence the seismic behaviour of buildings. The overall comparative analytical results presented in **Table 3** to **Table 5** and **Figure 9** clearly demonstrate the variation in structural response under different seismic zone conditions.

The major observations obtained from the analysis are summarized as follows:

1. Storey displacement and drift values increased progressively with increase in seismic zone intensity from Zone II to Zone IV.
2. The maximum displacement and drift values were observed in Part A models due to comparatively lower stiffness.
3. Part B models demonstrated improved seismic performance with reduced displacement and drift characteristics.
4. Base shear values increased significantly with increase in seismic intensity for all analytical models.

5. Part B models exhibited higher base shear and base reaction values due to larger seismic weight and plan dimensions.

6. Structural stiffness and plan configuration play a major role in controlling lateral deformation and seismic response of high-rise RC buildings.

The results obtained from the present investigation indicate that buildings with improved stiffness and optimized plan dimensions provide better seismic resistance and structural stability under earthquake loading conditions.

CONCLUSION

The present study focused on the comparative seismic analysis of reinforced concrete (RC) high-rise framed buildings subjected to earthquake loading under Seismic Zone II, Zone III, and Zone IV conditions using ETABS. A total of six analytical models categorized into Part A and Part B configurations were evaluated to study the influence of plan dimensions and structural stiffness on seismic performance. Based on the analytical results obtained from the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The seismic response of the buildings increased significantly with increase in seismic zone intensity from Zone II to Zone IV. Higher seismic zones produced greater displacement, storey drift, and base shear values for all analytical models.

2. The maximum storey displacement observed in the study was 272.198 mm for the Part A model under Seismic Zone IV conditions, whereas the corresponding displacement for the Part B model was 175.514 mm. The Part B model showed approximately **35.5% lower displacement** compared to the Part A model, indicating improved lateral stiffness and better seismic performance.

3. The maximum storey drift recorded for the Part A model was 0.010253, while the Part B model exhibited a lower drift value of 0.006638 under identical seismic loading conditions. The Part B configuration reduced storey drift by approximately **35.3%**, demonstrating better resistance against earthquake-induced deformation.

4. The base shear values increased progressively with increase in seismic intensity. For the Part A model, the base shear increased from 4405.96 kN in Zone II to 9913.42 kN in Zone IV. Similarly, the Part B model exhibited base shear values ranging from 10874 kN to 24466 kN. The Part B model developed approximately **146.8% higher base shear** than the Part A model due to larger seismic weight and increased plan dimensions.

5. The maximum base reaction observed for the Part A model was 173617.56 kN, whereas the Part B model exhibited a base reaction value of 313286.08 kN. The Part B model showed approximately **80.4% higher base reaction** because of higher structural mass and load-carrying demand.

6. The comparative evaluation indicates that structural stiffness and plan configuration play a significant role in controlling seismic response parameters

such as displacement and storey drift. Buildings with improved stiffness demonstrated better structural stability and reduced lateral deformation under earthquake loading conditions.

7. The study confirms that varying beam and column sizes according to loading intensity and span conditions provides a more economical and structurally efficient design compared to adopting uniform sectional dimensions throughout the building.

8. The analytical results obtained from the present investigation may be useful for structural engineers and researchers in the planning, seismic analysis, and earthquake-resistant design of high-rise RC buildings located in different seismic zones in accordance with IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 [17].

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